

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

Harisha P.S.

Research Scholar, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad

And

K K Kadam

Asst. Prof. Department of Physical Education, Nutan College, Selu

Abstract :

Emotional intelligence is a by and large progressing social model, rising to unquestionable quality with Daniel Goleman's (1995) book called 'Emotional Intelligence'. The early emotional intelligence hypothesis was at first advanced during the 1970's and 1980's by the work and structures of examiners Howard Gardner Peter Salovey and John Mayer (1983). Emotional intelligence is a significant idea in HR orchestrating, position profiling, selection meeting and decision, the heads, client relations, client benefits generally speaking, regular day to day existence. Right when clinicians began to form and think about intelligence, they focused in on scholarly angles, for instance, memory and basic reasoning. Regardless, there were investigators who saw early that the non-scholarly perspectives were in like manner significant.

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eiirj/>

Introduction :

Emotional intelligence is the capacity to screen one's own and others' feelings, to isolate between different feelings and imprint them appropriately, and to use emotional information to control thinking and lead. According to Andrew N. Colman (2001), the term showed up inconsistently in the psychological literature during the 1970s and 1980s, however the idea was first officially characterized in 1990 by the US clinicians Peter Salovey and John D. Mayer, who later determined four gatherings of skills which incorporate: (a) the capacity to perceive, appraise, and express feelings precisely; (b) the capacity to get to and inspire feelings then they encourage perception, (c) the capacity to fathom emotional messages and to utilize emotional data; and (d) the capacity to direct one's own feelings to advance development and prosperity. Hence, the emotional intelligence as a develop, talks about emotional consistency, emotional competency and emotional development.

Methodology :

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To study the Emotional Intelligence on the performance of volleyball players.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study is

1. To investigate the level of Emotional Intelligence in sample subgroups.
2. To measure the impact of training on volleyball players' results.
3. To investigate the impact of socioeconomic status on volleyball players' success.
4. To investigate gender disparities in volleyball player success.

HYPOTHESES

The hypotheses of the study are:

1. There would be significant influence of training on the performance of volleyball players.
2. There would be significant difference in Emotional intelligence between sample sub-groups of independent variables.
3. There would be impact of socio economic status on the volleyball performance of the samples with varying levels of education and gender.
4. There would be significant correlation between independent variables on the performance of volleyball players.

Significance of the Study :

Emotional intelligence is the capacity to use emotions for productive works of an individual. The ability to recognize and identify one's own emotions and the ability to manage emotions in one self is essential for understanding one's own feelings and of others in the process of social interaction. This would rather help person for better adjustment, worth living and excellence in actions. It is needless to say that emotional intelligence is a booster for higher achievement of persons especially the students. Therefore, the students' higher achievement is largely believed to be influenced by the higher amount of emotional intelligence.

Table -1
The Sample distribution

SES	Male	Female	Total
High	50	50	100
Low	50	50	100
Total	100	100	200

Since before and after design is followed in the present investigation, attempt is made to administer an intervention of training, in order to examine its effect on the performance in before and after training conditions. This would enable researcher to study the impact of training on the performance of the sample.

INTERVENTION

An intervention strategy between the two conditions of testing was employed in the present study. In the place of emotional intelligence training, an alternative package of volleyball exercises was adopted to give training to sample of the present investigation. The volleyball exercise much pertinent to the constituents of emotional intelligence viz., perception of emotions, ability of reasoning, ability to understand, ability to manage, were selected consulting the experts in the field. Thus the sports and games performance of the sample in Volley Ball team event was measured twice i.e., in before and after training.

The following Asanas were performed during the training in order to develop the Emotional Intelligence.

Asnas benefits in volleyball:

Yoga is as a rule just considered as a method of calming down and relaxing, however it has a lot a bigger number of advantages than those two. Yoga includes various moves, stretching, breathing control, and straightforward reflection. And keeping in mind that it appears to be that yoga has been discussed more as of late, it bears rehashing that it's a training that is exceptionally old with roots following back to old India.

Dancer

Dancer pose helps with hip mobility, stability, and single leg balance. Tight hip flexors and round shoulders are common complaints among volleyball players. It's important not to hyperextend your knee or arch your lower back when performing this pose. This would have an effect on the ability to stretch the targeted areas.

Wide-legged Squatter

When playing volleyball, you must be able to maintain a low, squatted posture at all times during the game. The wide-legged squatter yoga pose helps volleyball players maintain their balance and flexibility. It targets specific muscle groups such as the back, calves, abductors, and hamstrings.

Reverse Plank

An opposite plank is thought for anybody, particularly a volleyball player, to add solidarity to their center. It additionally reinforces our lower chain – glutes, hamstrings, and lower back. These territories are vital for volleyball athletes and keep that all around extended and solid.

Threading-The-Needle-Twist

In volleyball our bodies rotate a great deal, explicitly our torso and shoulders. This incredible yoga pose assists with torso versatility and shoulder flexibility. Since these territories are utilized continually in volleyball, utilizing this yoga pose can help forestall harm and conceivable tearing.

Pigeon Forward Fold

This is an extraordinary method to stretch and calm down during a post practice or post game cool down. It helps stretch and add flexibility to the hip, lower back, and lats. The lower back can be a weak

region for volleyball players if not extended as expected and utilizing strategies like this can help forestall damage to the territory.

Tools

The tests that were used in this study are as follows:

1) Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS)

This EI scale is developed by Goleman in the year 1995, which consists of 30 items in its short form version which is used in the present study. This consists of seven alternate responses ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The scoring is performed by hand. The scale's reliability and validity are satisfactory and sufficient.

2) Socio-Economic-Status Scale (SESS)

The Socio-Economic-Status Scale was developed by B. Gupta et al in the year 1984 and this scale was used in this study to assess the participants' social, educational, professional, and economic perspectives. Scoring was performed in compliance with the manual's guidelines.

3) Volleyball Skill Test by Brady's

Brady's Volleyball Skills Test : Brady constructed a volleyball skill on 537 college men volleyballers. The test-retest reliability coefficient is reported 14.9 while the validity coefficient has been reported to be 0.86. The test was made to measure general volleyball playing ability of college men
Equipment: Standard inflated volleyballs, wall marking chalk, tapes, stopwatch and pair of staircases for support to mark the target.

DELIMITATIONS

1. The study was delimited to the selected events like Volley ball performance.
2. The factors selected were delimited for two classifications of independent variables.
3. The study was delimited to UG and PG level of education.
4. The study was delimited to the affiliated colleges of Aurangabad University .
5. The study is further delimited to at least participated in inter-collegiate tournaments of Aurangabad University.

RESULTS :

The present study attempts to explore the role of emotional intelligence in increasing sports performance of players selected randomly from various colleges of Aurangabad University. The sample was matched for education, gender and other independent variables like SES etc. In the present study before and after design was adopted keeping training as an intervention.

Table - 2

Influence of Independent Variables on Volley Ball Game: (ANOVA) F-ratios (N = 200)

Main Effects	DF	SOS	MS	F
Education	1	824.885	824.885	2.191
Gender	1	292.83	292.83	2.068
SES	1	780.01	780.01	2.180
Emotional Intelligence	1	891.32	891.32	2.191
Interactions				
Education and Gender	1	864.196	864.196	2.200
Education and SES	1	859.505	859.505	2.199
Gender and SES	1	907.477	907.477	2.210
Education and EI	1	846.425	846.425	2.410
Gender and EI	1	714.13	714.13	2.406
SES and EI	1	857.456	857.456	2.46

*Significant at 0.05 level.

Table — 2 gives 'F ratio for Volley Ball event. The independent variables of study include levels of education of gender, emotional intelligence and SES. The 'f' ratio for the education on main effect is 2.191 which is significant beyond 0.05 level. This shows that education has a major influence on the athletic output of samples in a volleyball game. Therefore the level of education makes a difference in the ability to achieve higher results.

Table - 3

Shows r-values between variables and Volleyball test

Variables	r-values
Education x Volleyball	0.25**
Genders x Volleyball	0.17*
Socio-Economic-Status x Volleyball	0.25*
Emotional Intelligence x Volleyball	0.30**

** Significant at 0.01 level.

* Significant at 0.05 level.

The results given in the Table – 3 clearly reveal that r-values between education and volleyball test, genders and volleyball test, socio-economic-status and volleyball, and emotional intelligence (post-test scores) and volleyball tests are all positive and significant. This clearly indicates the performance of the sample in the volleyball test is highly correlated with the levels of education, genders, socio-

economic-status and emotional intelligence. Thus higher level education, high socio-economic-status, and higher emotional intelligence are significant correlates of volleyball performance.

CONCLUSIONS :

The major conclusions of this study are as follows:

1. There is a significant difference in the emotional intelligence between the UG and PG sub-groups: The emotional intelligence of PG students is substantially higher than that of UG students.
2. Players from both the PG and UG levels demonstrated substantially higher emotional intelligence after practicing than before.
3. There is a significant difference in the emotional intelligence between pre-training condition and post- training condition in male sub-group and in female sub-group.
4. The respondents belonging to high Socio-Economic-Status (SES) and low SES has reveals significantly higher emotional intelligence (EI) after training than before training.
5. The high SES groups, has significantly higher emotional intelligence than the low Socio-Economic-Status after receiving.
6. There is a significant impact of training on volleyball performance of volleyball test as the post training scores in volleyball test are significantly lower than the pre- training condition in the sample of PG level and UG level.
7. The UG volleyball players took substantially less time in the volleyball test than the PG volleyball players.
8. In the post-training volleyball evaluation, there is a significant gender difference.
9. The learning has resulted in substantially improved volleyball results in both male and female classes.
10. In a volleyball test, there is a substantial effect of training on the sports performance of a high SES sample.
11. The higher SES samples have significantly higher performance than the low SES in volleyball test.
12. There is significant influence of education on volleyball test: The PG students are significantly higher than the UG students in volleyball test.
13. There is significant influence of gender on volleyball test.
14. There is impact of SES on volleyball test.
15. Emotional intelligence has significantly influenced the volleyball performance of the players in volleyball event.
16. There are interaction effects of all the independent variables on volleyball test.
17. There is a significant influence of emotional intelligence on volleyball performance of players.

References:

- Bar-On, Reuven; Parker, James DA (2000). *The Handbook of Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Development, Assessment, and Application at Home, School, and in the Workplace*. San Francisco, California: Jossey-Bass. ISBN 0787949841. pp. 40-59.
- Bosnar, Ksenija (2002). Emotional intelligence and sports achievement, *Kinesiology — new perspectives* / Milanovic, Dragan, Prot, Franjo (ed). Part of a CC Journal, pp. 742- 745.
- Kaplan, Fran Beth (2004) *Educating the emotions: Emotional intelligence training for early childhood teachers and caregivers*. School Cardinal Stretch University, Degree.
- Salovey, P. & Mayer, J.D. (1990) "Emotional intelligence" *Imagination, Cognition, and Personality*, 9, 185-211.
- Alderman, R.B. (1974). *Psychological Behaviour in Sport*. W.B. Saunders Company, Toronto.
- Andersen, M. B. (2000). *Doing sport psychology*. Champaign, IL: *Human Kinetics*.
- Esfangreh, A.S. (2011). Effect of six weeks polymeric exercise on dynamic postural control of male athletic students. *Annals of Biological Research*, 2(6), pp. 88-90.
- John W. Best James V. Khan (2012) 10th Edition *Research in Education* Phi Learning Private limited, New Delhi.
- Kothari C.R. (2004) *Research Methodology methods and Technique* 2^{ed} Edition New Age International Publisher, New Delhi.
- Miller, P.B. and Miller, A.J., "Psychological Correlates of Success in Elite Sports Women", *International journal of Sport psychology*, Vol. XVI, No.6, (1985).
- Parvinder Singh. (2012). Comparative study of selected physiological and anthropometrical variables of Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players of Haryana. Ph.D., Thesis, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak.
- Ross, J.S. and Wilson, K.S., *Foundation of Anatomy and Physiology*, Edinburgh: The English Book Society Churchill Living Stone, 1973.
- Shaver, Larry G., *Essentials of Exercise Physiology*, Delhi: Surjeet Publication, 1981.
- Singh, "Psychological Characteristics of Top Level of Indian Sportsmen", cited by Sidhuet *al.*, *Sports Sciences Health, Fitness and Performance*.
- Terry Mc Morris (2004) *Acquisition and Performance of Sports Skills*. University College Chichester, UK.
- Vishan Singh Rathore, ArvindBahadur Singh. (2014). Analysis of physical and physiological parameters of Kabaddi and Kho-Kho inter-varsity players. *American Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*, 2(5A) : 13-16.